

slightly higher locations (medium high to medium low lands).

6. Farmers normally used low or even no potassic fertilizers during the last few years.

7. Rice is cultivated continuously in almost all three seasons in some places. Usually only Paiam, the susceptible var-

ety, is used for three consecutive seasons.

In addition to the above factors, the development of new virulent races of the highly variable causal fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* and the immigration to Bangladesh of spores of races different from those already present are also possible.

Thus, the identification of the new races and of the number of races existing in Bangladesh and efforts to find chemical control measures are immediate steps being taken in the research programs of the BRRI Pathology Division. Studies on the interaction of ufra and blast have also been undertaken. ■

Varietal and insecticidal trial against rice tungro virus

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A trial with 10 test cultivars, which aimed at determining the effect of insecticidal treatment on the control of the vector insect of rice tungro virus (RTV), was laid out in split plots with 3 replications during 1979 thaladi. The treatments were: root soaking with FMC 35001 24% EC at 0.04% along with 1% urea for 20 minutes, maximum protection in which carbofuran 3% G was applied at 0.5 kg a.i./ha 10, 25, and 45 days after transplanting (DT); and an untreated control.

ADT 32 and AD 7211 had low percentages of RTV while ADT 31 and AD 9105 had high percentages (see table).

Data on rice tungro virus (RTV) incidence from an insecticidal trial, Tamil Nadu, India, 1979 thaladi.

Variety	RTV incidence (%)			Mean
	Root soaking	Max protection	Control	
AD 10969	56.0	52.3	52.0	53.4
AD 7211	25.3	22.0	27.7	25.0
TKM 9	39.3	35.3	41.7	38.8
AD 6120	62.7	63.7	60.7	62.4
AD 12599	68.7	58.7	67.3	64.9
ADT 32	33.3	10.3	22.3	22.0
ASD 15	42.7	14.3	46.0	34.3
IR20	56.3	16.3	45.3	39.3
ADT 31	92.3	93.0	100.0	95.1
AD 9105	97.7	92.7	100.0	96.8
Mean	57.4	45.9	56.3	

C.D. (P = 0.05%)	Insecticidal treatment	Varieties	Interaction
	2.3	5.4	3.2

In seven varieties – ADT 31, AD 9105, AD 6120, AD 12599, AD 10969, TKM 9 and AD 7211 – insecticidal treatment did not appreciably reduce RTV incidence by controlling the vector

insects.

In IR20, ASD15, and ADT32, maximum protection gave good reduction of RTV. ■

Outbreak of glume discoloration in Haryana, India

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Grain spotting, also known as glume discoloration (GLD) or dirty panicle, appears sporadically each crop season in Haryana on Basmati 370 and late-emerging panicles of IR8 and Jaya. Seventy-two percent discolored grains was recorded on RP967-4-1-10 and 31.5% in Basmati 370 in the 1978 wet season. Of the mycoflora associated with harvested grains, *Trichoconis padwickii* (in 60-80% discolored grains) was predominant over *Curvularia lunata*, *Drechslera oryzae*, *Phoma* sp., *Fusarium*

semitectum, *F. moniliforme*, and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

A glume discoloration outbreak occurred in September 1979, after a long drought followed by rainfall and a storm when the crop was in the panicle-emergence stage. All emerging panicles

had dirty brown or black grains. Symptoms appeared before the milk stage, and caused farmers to fear that they would not even get seed for their next crop. Pollen grains were viable, but no one could predict if grains would form. High sterility of spikelets and their

Occurrence of glume discoloration (GLD) under natural conditions at the Kaul Rice Research Station, India, in 1979 kharif.

Score	GLD (%)	No.	Cultivars showing discoloration	
			%	Designation
1	<1	110	38	Improved Sona, PAU1-608A, Sabarmati, R36-2486
3	1-5	58	20	Pusa 2-21, Prasad
5	5-25	35	12	Palman 579, Sona, Badshah Pasand
7	25-50	37	13	Basmati 370, IR36, PR106
9	>50	60	20	Ratna, Jaya, RP967-4-7-4, RP967-4-1-10, RP967-11-4-22